

Constituents from *Ixora finlaysoniana*

Deepa Chauhan*, Aditi Gupta, Nidhi Srivastava and J. Singh

Chemistry Department, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 18 November 2004, revised 7 October 2005, accepted 8 November 2005

Abstract : Phytochemical investigation of *Ixora finlaysoniana* (Linn.) leads to the isolation and identification of two new triterpenoids 3-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2 α ,19 α -dihydroxyurs-12-ene-28 oic acid- β -D-glucopyranosyl ester (1) and 2 α ,3 α ,19 α -trihydroxyurs-12-ene-28-oic acid- β -D-galactopyranosyl ester (2) based on chemical and spectroscopic studies.

Keyword : *Ixora finlaysoniana*, Rubiaceae, whole plant, triterpenoid saponins.

Ixora finlaysoniana Linn. (Rubiaceae) is a member of the genus of highly medicinal plant^{1,2} in the indigenous system of medicine. The ethanolic extract of this whole plant afforded two new compounds along with three known compounds viz. epigenin-4'-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, 11-hydroxy-dodec-5-en-2-one and β -sitosterol.

The water soluble portion of the ethanolic extract of the whole plant material on extraction with ethylacetate gave compound 1 and 2. Compound 1 was obtained as a light yellow crystal, m.p. 257–259°. It gave positive colorations in the Liebermann-Buchard and Molish test for triterpenoid saponins. The IR spectrum showed the absorption for hydroxyl group (3425 cm⁻¹) ester carbonyl 1735 cm⁻¹ and double bond 1645 cm⁻¹. Acid hydrolysis (refluxing 15% HCl containing some benzene) of 1 afforded D-glucose. The mass spectrum gave a peak at *m/z* at 812, corresponding to the molecular formula C₄₂H₆₈O₁₅. ¹³C NMR spectral data indicates that compound 1 possesses 7 methyl, 10 methylene, 17 methine and 8 quaternary carbons. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of 1 showed a downfield shift of C-3 (δ 88.8) compared with rosamutin (83.9). This shift can be interpreted as due to the linkage of a glucose moiety at C-3. The ¹H NMR spectrum showed two anomeric protons of glucoses at 6.30 and 6.27 (d, *J* 8 Hz, each 1H) indicative of the linkage of two glucosyl moieties with the aglycone in the β configuration (the larger *J* value of glucose indicated that the anomeric center had β configuration). Thus compound 1 was 3-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-2 α ,19 α -dihydroxyurs-12-ene-28 oic acid- β -D-glucopyranosyl ester.

Compound 2 was obtained as an amorphous powder m.p. 193–195°. Many features in its IR, EI mass spec-

trum³ and ¹³C NMR spectra indicated that it is closely related in structure of rosamutin⁴. The ¹H NMR spectrum of 2 showed signals for H-12 at δ 5.26 (1H, br s), H-2 at 5.53 (1H, br s), H-3 at 3.29 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz) and H-18 at 2.95 (1H, s). Acid hydrolysis of 2 afforded D-galactose identified by GC which was linked to C-28. This was 2 α ,3 β ,19 α -trihydroxyurs 12-ene-28 oic acid- β -D-galactopyranosyl ester.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected, column and thin layer paper chromatographic analyses were performed at room temperature. Sugars were characterised by descending paper chromatography on Whatmann no.1 paper, using n-butanol-acetic acid water (9 : 1.5, v/v) as a developing solvent. The whole plant was obtained from the local city of Allahabad and identified by the Botany Department, Allahabad.

The air dried and powdered plant of *Ixora finlaysoniana* was extracted with EtOH under reflux for 15 days. The extract on keeping in a refrigerator gave a white deposit which was filtered. The filtrate after further concentration was poured into a large excess of water and the mixture stirred. The water soluble fraction on extraction with ethyl acetate gave an ethyl acetate soluble fraction which when chromatographed repeatedly over silica gel columns gave a light yellow colored compound 1. The white deposit after refluxing with methanol gave methanol soluble portion which when extracted with hexane : ethylacetate afforded compound 2 (10 mg).

Compound 1 : The ethyl acetate extract of the water soluble portion was purified over a column of silica gel and crystallized as light yellow needles from ethyl ace-

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR Spectral data of compounds **1**, **2**, rosamutin (100 MHz, δ in ppm from TMS, pyridine- d_5 as solvent)

C	1	2	Rosamutin
1	47.2 (t)	49.7 (t)	47.9
2	68.6 (d)	68.7 (d)	68.6
3	88.8 (d)	83.9 (d)	83.9
4	37.6 (s)	38.6 (s)	38.5
5	56.0 (d)	56.0 (d)	56.0
6	18.2 (t)	19.1 (t)	19.1
7	33.5 (t)	33.6 (t)	33.5
8	40.6 (s)	40.7 (s)	40.6
9	47.9 (d)	48.0 (d)	48.0
10	38.3 (s)	38.9 (s)	39.6
11	24.2 (t)	24.2 (t)	24.2
12	128.3 (d)	128.4 (d)	128.4
13	139.3 (s)	139.3 (s)	139.3
14	42.3 (s)	42.2 (s)	42.1
15	29.1 (t)	29.5 (t)	29.4
16	26.6 (t)	26.2 (t)	26.1
17	48.5 (s)	48.8 (s)	48.6
18	54.4 (d)	54.4 (d)	54.4
19	72.5 (s)	72.7 (s)	72.7
20	42.1 (d)	42.2 (d)	42.1
21	26.0 (t)	27.0 (t)	27.0
22	37.5 (t)	37.9 (t)	37.7
23	28.7 (q)	29.4 (q)	29.2
24	17.7 (q)	17.7 (q)	17.7
25	16.6 (q)	17.7 (q)	17.6
26	17.2 (q)	17.1 (q)	17.0
27	24.6 (q)	24.7 (q)	24.6
28	176.6 (s)	176.9 (s)	176.9
29	26.9 (q)	26.8 (q)	26.7
30	15.5 (q)	16.7 (q)	16.7
Sugar moieties :			
	Glc-28	Gal-28	Glc-28
1	95.7 (d)	95.7 (d)	95.8
2	72.8 (d)	74.6 (d)	74.0
3	78.6 (d)	74.7 (d)	78.9
4	71.2 (d)	68.8 (d)	71.3
5	79.1 (d)	75.3 (d)	79.2
6	62.0 (t)	62.6 (t)	62.4
	Glc-3		
1	108.1 (d)		
2	73.9 (d)		
3	78.6 (d)		
4	72.0 (d)		
5	79.1 (d)		
6	62.3 (t)		

tate benzene fraction (2 : 7, v/v). ^1H NMR (pyridine- d_5 TMS) δ 6.30 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1 of glc-3), 6.27 (d, J 8 Hz, H-1 of glc-28), 5.54 (1H, m, H-2 β), 5.24 (1H, br s, H-12), 4.60–4.00 (12H, m, sugar H), 3.24 (1H, d, J 8.6 Hz, H-3 α), 2.93 (1H, s, H-18), 1.38, 1.34, 1.29, 1.14, 1.10, 0.98 (6 \times 3H, s, H-23-27, H-29), 1.07 (3H, d, J 6.1 Hz, H-30). ^{13}C NMR see Table 1. EI MS m/z , M^+ 812, 422 ($M-2 \times$ glc), 279, 264, 218, 201, 146. FAB MS (m/z) : 835 [$M + \text{Na}$] $^+$, 488 [$M-2\text{glc}$] $^+$, 470, 452, 407, 391.

R_1 (1) β -D-glucose
(2) H
 R_2 β -D-glucose
 β -D-galactose

Compound 2 : The methanol soluble portion eluted with hexane : ethylacetate (7 : 3) were chromatographed over silica gel gave an amorphous powder. ^1H NMR (pyridine- d_5 TMS) δ 6.31 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz, H-1 of gal), 5.53 (1H, br, H-26), 5.26 (1H, br s, H-12), 3.29 (1H, d, J 9.3 Hz, H-3 α), 2.95 (1H, s, H-18) 1.69, 1.38, 1.29, 1.19, 1.10, 1.06 (6 \times 3H, s, H-23-H-27, H-29), 1.50 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz, H-30). ^{13}C NMR see Table 1. EIMS m/z , [$M\text{-gal}$] $^+$ 442, 264, 246, 218, 201, 187, 146.

Hydrolysis of compound 1 and 2 : Each compound (2 mg), 15% HCl (5 ml) and benzene (5 ml) were mixed and refluxed for 10 h. After neutralization of the aq. layer, the solution was filtered and concentrated. D-Glucose in compound **1** was identified by PC. D-Galactose in compound **2** was detected by PC and GC (trimethyl silylates D-galactose); column : hp-19; inj. temp. : 262; column temp. : 160; flow rate 50 ml min^{-1} ; instrument : GC-9AM. Galactose, R_f , 6.2 min (standard 6.6 min).

References

1. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 1935, Vol. 2, 1286.
2. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, "Glassary of Indian Medicinal Plants", 1936, 143.
3. H. Budzikiewicz, J. M. Wilson and C. Djerassi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3688.
4. H. Q. Du, *Acta Pharmaceutical Sinica*, 1983, **18**, 314.